

**ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL STUDY OF ANTIPYRETIC IN THE SERANGPANJANG
REGION, SUBANG, WEST JAVA, INDONESIA**

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ABSTRACT

Many plants are being traditionally used in the treatment of fever and their antipyretic activities have been confirmed scientifically. This research aims to document and preserve the use of ethnomedicinal to treat fever by communities in the Serangpanjang Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia. Fieldwork was carried out from May to June 2025 using direct interviews, questionnaires and discussions. Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature. The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system. Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org). This research reports that there are 30 plant species commonly used by people in the Serangpanjang Region for fever treatment. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (63.3%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (20%), fruit (10%), stems, and rhizomes (3.3% respectively). Meanwhile, the preparation methods most frequently used were decoction (53.3%) and infusion (46.7%). The results of this research confirm that people in the Serangpanjang Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of fever with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

KEYWORDS: Traditional medicine, Ethnomedicinal plants, Serangpanjang Region, Antipyretic.

INTRODUCTION

The hypothalamus regulates body temperature with a delicate balance between heat production and heat loss through the set-point control. Infection, tissue damage, inflammation, graft rejection, malignancy and other disease may elevate the set point to induce fever.^[1] Fever is a complex physiologic response which triggered by abnormalities in the brain, toxic substances that affect temperature regulation, bacterial infections, brain tumors, and dehydration. Elevation of the body temperature occurs when the concentration of prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) increases within parts of the brain. The mechanism of antipyretic drugs is inhibit the cyclooxygenase (COX) activity and consequently

reducing the levels of PGE2. Synthetic antipyretic drugs have side effects.^[2] Therefore, it is worth to searching herbal medicines that are equally efficacious and comparatively side effects free, as substitutes for synthetic drugs, such as paracetamol.^[3] Indonesia is the second largest country in the world with forest biodiversity, where there are 28,000 plant species and 2,500 of these species are medicinal plants.^[4-6] Currently, research to obtain new antipyretic drugs derived from natural ingredients continues to be carried out, one of which is through exploring active compounds from natural ingredients, especially medicinal plants which have traditionally been used by people to treat fever in various regions in Indonesia.^[7,8] One of the Region in

Indonesia that still uses herbal plants as an alternative treatment, especially for treating fever, is the Serangpanjang Region. This research aims to obtain detailed information about the use of herbal plants for alternative pain therapy in Serangpanjang Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia using a field survey method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Serangpanjang is located in Subang Regency, West Java, Indonesia, with an area of 1,311,844 km². This area has an altitude of 1,000 meters above sea level with an average maximum air temperature of 31°C and a minimum of 21°C. Moreover, it is located between 06°41'49" South Latitude and 107°35'50" East Longitude. This region is a tropical climate area that is mostly inhabited by Sundanese tribes (90%) and other tribes (10%). Vegetation in the study area is in humid conditions with an average rainfall of 3,000 mm/year.

Data Collection

An extensive field survey was carried out to obtain information about medicinal plants from the Sundanese tribe in the study area. To document existing information about medicinal plants from tribal practitioners, several field visits were conducted from May to June 2025 in the Serangpanjang Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia. During the research, ethnomedicinal information was collected from middle-aged and older tribal practitioners in their local language (Sundanese), through direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Information on local names of plants, plant parts used, preparation methods and administration routes (e.g., infusion, paste, juice and decoction) of all ethnomedicinal plants collected were recorded during the survey period.

Botanical Identification

Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature.^[9] The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system, except for Pteridophyta and Gymnospermae.^[10] Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org).

Ethics Statement

All participants provided verbal consent before the interview and gave consent to publish the information they provided.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed that 30 plant species are commonly used by local people to treat fever (Table 1). This shows that the study location is affordable in terms of biodiversity. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (63.3%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (20%), fruit (10%), stems, and rhizomes (3.3% respectively). The use of leaves is reported to be easier to prepare and easier to extract active substances from them for treatment. At the same time, leaves have less effect on the mother plant.^[11] Meanwhile, the preparation methods most frequently used were decoction (53.3%) and infusion (46.7%). These results are in line with previous research which reported that the forms of traditional medicine most widely used by the community were decoctions and infusions.^[9]

Table 1: Ethnomedicinal plants, local name, part used, mode of administration, and dosage uses in Serangpanjang, Subang, West Java, Indonesia.

No	Species	Family	Local name	Parts used	Mode of administration	Dosage of use
1	<i>Allium cepa</i> L.	Amaryllidaceae	Bawang Bombai	Rhizome	Decoction	80 grams once a day
2	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Alliaceae	Bawang Putih	Rhizome	Infusion	20 grams once a day
3	<i>Alpinia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Lengkuas	Rhizome	Decoction	50 grams once a day
4	<i>Annona muricata</i> L.	Annonaceae	Sirsak	Leaf	Infusion	100 grams once a day
5	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Annonaceae	Srikaya	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
6	<i>Averrhoa carambola</i> L.	Oxalidaceae	Belimbing	Fruit	Infusion	100 mL once a day
7	<i>Centella asiatica</i> L.	Apiaceae	Pegagan	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
8	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J.Presl	Lauraceae	Kayu Manis	Stem	Decoction	100 grams once a day
9	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kunyit	Rhizome	Infusion	200 grams once a day
10	<i>Cymbopogon nardus</i>	Poaceae	Sereh Wangi	Leaf	Infusion	50 grams once a day
11	<i>Durio zibethinus</i> Murr.	Bombacaceae	Durian	Leaf	Infusion	100 grams once a day
12	<i>Elephantopus scaber</i> L.	Asteraceae	Tapak Liman	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
13	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> L.	Clusiaceae	Manggis	Rind	Infusion	80 mL once a day
14	<i>Kaempferia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kencur	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
15	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Pare	Leaf	Decoction	40 grams once a day
16	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Mengkudu	Fruit	Infusion	50 grams once a day
17	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	Moringaceae	Kelor	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day

18	<i>Morus L.</i>	Moraceae	Murbei	Leaf	Infusion	50 grams once a day
19	<i>Musa paradisiaca L.</i>	Musaceae	Pisang	Leaf	Infusion	50 grams once a day
20	<i>Ocimum basilicum L.</i>	Lamiaceae	Kemangi	Leaf	Decoction	300 grams once a day
21	<i>Orthosiphon stamineus Benth</i>	Lamiaceae	Kumis Kucing	Leaf	Infusion	40 mL once a day
22	<i>Pandanus amaryllifolius Roxb.</i>	Pandanaceae	Pandan Wangi	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
23	<i>Phaleria macrocarpa (Scheff.) Boerl)</i>	Thymelaceae	Mahkota Dewa	Fruit	Decoction	10 grams once a day
24	<i>Phyllanthus acidus (L.) Skeels</i>	Phyllanthaceae	Cermai	Leaf	Infusion	100 grams once a day
25	<i>Phyllanthus niruri L.</i>	Phyllanthaceae	Meniran	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
26	<i>Piper betle L.</i>	Piperaceae	Sirih	Leaf	Decoction	200 grams once a day
27	<i>Psidium guajava L.</i>	Myrtaceae	Jambu biji	Leaf	Decoction	20 grams once a day
28	<i>Syzygium cumini (L.) Skeels</i>	Myrtaceae	Jamblang	Leaf	Infusion	150 grams once a day
29	<i>Syzygium polyanthum (Wight) Walpers</i>	Myrtaceae	Salam	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
30	<i>Zingiber officinale Rosc.</i>	Zingiberaceae	Jahe	Rhizome	Decoction	150 grams once a day

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research confirm that people in the Serangpanjang Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of fever with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

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